

Quantifying North Carolina Public Transit Gaps:

A Geographic Information Systems Analysis of Public Transportation Need and Spending

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GEOG 697: Geography Capstone

13 April 2026

Introduction

The Problem

Public transportation systems provide greater access to services and opportunities throughout the community. In the United States specifically, these systems are typically seen as an alternative to private transportation and are only utilized by impoverished populations. Regardless of the stigma surrounding public transit, there are specific, tangible economic benefits to both individual households and the community at large. Studies that analyze how transit expansion impact economic activity have found that neighborhoods within 0.5 miles of a stop enjoy a 39% bump in the labor force participation rate (Kim, 2021). In the same vein, research has found that cities with transit systems have 10% lower commute times as well as 0.44% higher GDP (Yu et al., 2020). A similar study found that household income improved by 3.4% because of greater access to employment opportunities (Sun, 2016).

Outside of economics, there are also specific social benefits to investing in public transportation. Either through fixed route services or through on demand transportation, seniors or others with mobility issues rely on transit to access medical appointments, grocery stores, or other day-to-day chores. A study published within the past year found that communities without public systems have higher rates of missed medical appointments and a reduced likelihood of people even seeking healthcare in the first place (Alhassan, 2025). Regardless of a community's size, public transport provides across a wide range of sectors and demographic groups.

However, the North Carolina Triad is largely missing out on these benefits – both economic and social. Winston-Salem, for example, is one of the most segregated cities in the United States. Among Winston-Salem Transit Authority (WSTA) riders, 80% lack a car and 69% have an annual income less than 20,000 USD (Blizard, 2018). Without WSTA, these people would be unable to access their already limited job opportunities. With the current, limited system Forsyth County ranks in the bottom three counties in the United States for upwards economic mobility. Next door, Greensboro and High Point face similar challenges. Very few metro areas in the state provide their citizens with adequate transportation, especially in minority dominated city centers, and the triad is no exception.

The Solution

Because of how affordable transportation impacts both economic mobility and the local economy, the Triad's lack of robust public transit systems constitutes a public policy problem. To address this policy gap, this analysis has four main objectives. **1)** Identify which US census tracts in the Triad have incongruencies between the public transportation spending and public transportation need relative to other peer North Carolina areas. **2)** Compare historical redlining maps with the modern-day census tracts identified as having noticeably less spending than need. **3)** Improve methods of spending distribution estimation by incorporating dasymetric aggregation methods into the areal interpolation process. **4)** And finally, create an online, interactive tool that

allows policymakers to interact with this analysis in a simple, easy to use format that allows this information to be seamlessly provided to those whose job it is to remedy these gaps.

Through these four objectives, this analysis will create a handful of downstream impacts. Firstly, very little academic research is focused on this region of North Carolina. Most projects focus on either the Triangle (Raleigh – Durham – Chapel Hill), Charlotte, or the state as a whole. By choosing to center this project on the Triad, this analysis will fill a currently existing gap, bridging both the public policy field with geography. Beyond just filling a geographic gap, this work will improve on existing areal interpolation methods and utilize a modified dasymetric aggregation to estimate where public transit networks spend their money. By generating accurate estimates with easily available public data sources, future work can estimate spending without having to scour the internet or request more detailed records enabling this type of research to be produced faster or analyze on units of analysis smaller than what is provided.

The most important impact of this project is that it builds upon the already existing, albeit limited, relationship between academia and the local governments of the Triad. By beginning to produce evidence-based analysis on policy problems that impact the region, researchers start to build trust with local policymakers and help to enact good policy in their communities. More specifically, however, this analysis creates an easy-to-use tool (Objective Four) to meet these officials on their terms. By creating this tool, I hope to allow policymakers to interact with this research without having to be fluent in data science terminology or statistics. This tool is hosted by ArcGIS Online and is called the [NC Transit Dashboard](#). Evidence-based policies are crucial for improving the day-to-day lives of our communities and above all else, this research aims to help elected officials in that endeavor.

Methodology

Data Selection

To determine which regions need public transportation in 2025, I replicated the input data from *Transportation Disadvantage Index* (TDI) used by the North Carolina Department of Transportation (NCDOT) to estimate transportation needs. The index used a combination of 7 variables: low-income population, BIPOC (black, indigenous, and people of color) population, zero-car households, youth aged 15 and under, seniors aged 65 and older, low English proficiency, and mobility-impaired adults (NCDOT, 2024). Additionally, I added two density related variables: population density and volume of traffic. These two variables help to capture the idea that denser regions have a higher need and are more suitable for public transportation than less dense areas. The updated data was downloaded from the American Community Survey (ACS) 2024 5-Year estimates which was released on 29 January 2026.

To gather data on public transportation system spending, I relied on the Federal Transit Administration (FTA). Any agency or company receiving FTA funding is required to submit

detailed annual financial reports (FTA, 2024). Using the FTA's transit agency profiles database, I recorded 2024 expenditure data for each agency operating within North Carolina and spatially joined this data to an NCDOT service area boundary shapefile to identify spending patterns across the state. Collectively, these datasets provided the necessary inputs to investigate transportation needs and the allocation of transportation resources.

I replicated this procedure on four levels of analysis: NC General Assembly (House and Senatorial districts), US Congressional districts of NC, and NC Counties. For the first three levels, the most up-to-date shapefiles were downloaded from the General Assembly's *Redistricting* page (NCGA, 2026). The geometry for NC Counties was downloaded from the US Census Bureau in the *Data Cleaning* step, along with the census tract boundaries.

Finally, to run the dasymetric analysis (discussed and explained in the following sections: *Data Aggregation* section and Appendix B), I used the National Land Cover Database (NLCD), a dataset produced by the United States Geological Survey (USGS). The NLCD classifies each 30x30-meter cell throughout the United States as a specific land-cover type. This dataset was clipped to the boundaries of North Carolina and downloaded via the Multi-Resolution Land Characteristics Consortium (MRLC) data viewer.

Data Cleaning

The American Community Survey data were accessed using the R package *tidycensus* (Walker, 2026) at the census tract level. Variables were subsequently cleaned and normalized as proportions exhibiting the specified characteristics using either population or number of households as the normalizing variable, depending on the specific needs of each of the seven variables, using the R package *tidyverse* (Wickham, 2019). The resulting dataset was then joined to a TIGER/Line census tract shapefile using the R package *sf* (Pebesma, 2023) to create the spatial layer used in future steps of this analysis.

The land cover data, on the other hand, was processed in the ArcGIS Pro desktop application. The data was first processed with the reclassify tool to compress the different land-cover types into a more concise representation. From there, the reclassify tool was used again to create a raster with 5 values: either 4 for Developed, High Intensity; 3 for Developed, Medium Intensity; 2 for Developed, Low Intensity; 1 for Developed, Open Space; and 0 for all other land-cover types. This process produced a raster that shows the location of developed vs. non-developed land, as well as differentiating among the intensities of development.

Data Aggregation

A consequence of integrating data from multiple public sources is that the units of analysis rarely coincide spatially. This introduces a well-known problem in geography called the

modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP), where different levels of aggregation reveal different trends entirely (Lee, 2025). Because these datasets are reported over different geographic boundaries, spatial interpolation is required to integrate them into a common set of target units. In the case of transferring values from one set of areal units to another, this creates an areal interpolation problem. As Lam (1983) notes, areal interpolation methods can be classified according to whether they preserve volume. Volume-preserving procedures ensure that the total value of the variable remains constant across the transformation, whereas non-volume preserving methods do not. To see a detailed exploration that explains the mathematical reasoning behind our decision to use a volume-preserving method over a non-volume-preserving method, consult Appendix A.

The specific volume-preserving method used in this analysis is dasymetric aggregation. Dasymetric maps, as Langford (1994) explains, are an alternative to traditional choropleth map techniques, which integrate remotely sensed data into the process to better estimate the distribution of a variable. Typical methods of volume-preserving aerial interpolation assume an even distribution of the variable throughout the source zone – the most common of which assumes even distribution with respect to land (Fisher, 1996). Pure dasymetric aggregation, on the other hand, assumes equal distribution with respect to developed land. While Langford used population as his variable of interest, I was able to adapt his method, using our eight different variables and using either census tracts or transit spending districts as the source zones and the four levels of analysis as target zones.

Our dasymetric model first masks undeveloped land and then calculates the area of developed land within both the target and source zones. Then, if the desired output is a weighted average, as in aggregating the poverty rate to an NC House district, for example, it calculates a weight using each of the four development tiers as the basis. Dasymetric aggregations, such as estimating spending across a US Congressional district, skip this weight-creation step. The result of this process is one value per variable requested for each target zone. To go more in depth than this explanation, or to view the equations underpinning this model, consult Appendix B. To view the dasymetric functions created to augment this process, consult this [GitHub repository](#) (Lackey, 2026).

Composite Indices Creation

This analysis includes two indices: the Principal Component Index (PCI) and the Spending Gap Index (SGI).

The first of the two indices created, and the most computationally intensive, is the PCI. The PCI is derived using principal component analysis (PCA), a multivariate method that extracts the most important information from the input variables, simplifies the description of the dataset, and investigates the relationships between the variables (Abdi, 2010). PCA achieves this

by reducing the dimensionality of the data while preserving as much variability as possible. It changes the variables into uncorrelated principal components (PCs), where the first few PCs explain most of the variation within the dataset (Jolliffe, 2002). These PCs are then associated with an eigenvalue, which represents the variance in the data explained by that component. PCA is commonly used for data reduction, exploratory analysis, and index construction. For a more detailed, non-scholarly explanation of the math behind PCA, consult this [Medium Article](#) (Swati, 2023).

To calculate the Principal Component Index (PCI), I used all North Carolina census tracts as input data, using PCs with eigenvalues greater than 1 according to the Kaiser criterion (Kaiser, 1960). In this case, the first three PCs were retained, which together explained approximately 72.79% of the total variance. The component loadings were used to derive the weights, which were then applied to the normalized input variables to compute the final PCI score. The full script containing this workflow is provided at this [GitHub repository](#) (Lackey, 2026) along with a table detailing the principal component output in Appendix C.

The Spending Gap Index (SGI) is a composite index that integrates both the PCI and the estimated total transit spending (in 2024 USD), combining them through a difference in standardized z-scores. A z-score transforms a variable so that it has a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one, allowing variables with different scales to be compared. For an observation x_i , the z-score is calculated as:

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{\sigma}$$

where the x_i is the observed value, \bar{x} is the population mean, and σ the population standard deviation. Through this normalization process, it becomes possible to compare these two very different units in an apples-to-apples manner (OECD, 2008). Specifically, the equation for the SGI subtracts the transit spending z-score z_s from the PCI z-score z_n so that:

$$SGI = z_n - z_s$$

By calculating the index in this manner, the SGI is calibrated so that a positive value indicates more need than spending, while a negative value indicates more spending than need.

To finalize the SGI, districts were classified into five categories based on their standardized scores. Districts with an SGI less than -1 were labeled as “*Very Good*,” while those with SGI between -1 and -0.5 were classified as “*Good*.” Districts with SGI between -0.5 and 0.5 were considered to have “*On Track*.” For districts with SGI between 0.5 and 1, the classification label was “*Poor*,” and districts with SGI greater than 1 were labeled as “*Very Poor*.” The language for these labels were chosen to prevent the idea that an area with an SGI above +0.5 had wasteful spending. In some cases, spending well over an SGI value of 0 is needed to receive the economic benefits mentioned in the introduction. The ultimate goal of the SGI is to be in the “*On Track*” category but any SGI value greater than -0.5 is acceptable.

Findings

Public Transportation Need

This results section will focus on two levels of aggregation: North Carolina Counties and United States Census Tracts. The other levels of aggregation can be viewed and examined at the website ([NC Transit Dashboard](#)).

There were five counties that received a need designation higher than “Moderate Need,” two of which were classified as “Very High Need.” These two, Forsyth and Guilford, are the largest two counties by population and house Winston-Salem, Greensboro, and High Point. Forsyth and Guilford counties have the highest need (compared to the state’s baseline) because of their much higher population density, minority rate, and poverty rates. The remaining nine counties all had public transit need either moderate or lower meaning that they are either in line with the state’s baseline need or below it. Figure 1 maps the county PCI clipped to the Triad boundaries, giving labels ascending from “Very Low Need” to “Very High Need” assigned with respect to five natural breaks divisions.

Figure 1

North Carolina Triad Counties Principal Component Index Map

Note: This figure shows the distribution of Public Transit Need throughout the 12 counties of the Triad.

The distribution of public transit need at the census tract level is far more clustered into dense urban city centers than is apparent on the county level map. Specifically, tracts with high or very high need tend to be situated in downtown Winston-Salem, Greensboro, and High Point with most of these tracts located in majority minority census tracts. This distribution reflects historical redlining maps with southern and eastern Greensboro and East Winston having the most need throughout the region. On the flip side, the Triad’s rural tracts have very little public transit need driven by low population density, relatively lower poverty rates, and greater access to vehicles. Figure 2 maps the tract PCI values and shows the distribution of need throughout the region.

Figure 2

North Carolina Triad Census Tracts Principal Component Index Map

Note: This figure shows the distribution of Public Transit Need throughout the 469 US Census Tracts of the Triad.

Public Transportation Spending

For the purposes of calculating public transportation spending per geographic unit, this analysis used spending per capita which compares rural and urban areas better than gross spending. The disruption of public transit spending is like the public transit need map where 5 counties were given a category above “*Moderate Spending.*” Forsyth and Guilford counties remained in the top category of “*Very High*” driven by large transportation systems in each of the three main cities. Alamance county has high spending because it receives both Go Triangle and Piedmont Authority for Regional Transportation (PART) funding while Stokes County spends money on local busing for seniors. Figure 3 is a map which displays the distribution of per capita public transit spending throughout the region.

Figure 3

North Carolina Triad County Public Transit Spending Map

Note: This figure shows the distribution of public transit spending per capita throughout the 12 Triad Counties.

The distribution of per capital spending by US Census Tracts is very different from the distribution in the county map. This is mostly because of the modifiable areal unit problem along with most areas having extremely low spending. The few tracts that are “*Moderate Spending*” or

above are primarily located in western Winston-Salem and Greensboro along with the city’s suburbs. Unlike with the public transit need, the eastern parts of these two cities are either “Moderate Spending” or “Low Spending” leaving a potential spending gap. For nearly all rural tracts, they are dark green, indicating next to zero dollars per capita for the residents. Figure 4 displays the distribution of per capita spending throughout the region via another map.

Figure 4

North Carolina Triad Census Tracts Public Transit Spending Map

Note: This figure shows the distribution of public transit spending per capita throughout the 469 Triad US Census Tracts.

Spending Gap Index

The Spending Gap Index (SGI) is structured so that if a region has a spending z-score of +1 and a need z-score of +1 as well, the SGI will equal 0. Figure 5 displays the distribution of the spending gap index. As mentioned in the note, a county with a shade of green has, on average, more spending than need, whereas a county with a shade of orange has just the opposite. For the 12 Triad counties, 5 of them are a shade or orange (Forsyth, Guilford, Alamance, Rockingham, and Caswell) while only 1 (Stokes) is a shade of green. While this does

give some insight into general trends across the region, because of the level of aggregation very little insight is offered into intra-city dynamics/

Figure 5

North Carolina Triad County Spending Gap Index (SGI) Map

Note: This figure shows the distribution of the Spending Gap Index (SGI) throughout the 12 Triad Counties. A value of Good or Very Good means higher spending than need, a value of On Track means adequate spending for need, and a value of Poor or Very Poor means lower spending than need.

Figure 6 displays the SGI aggregated to individual US Census Tracts and shows a very different distribution than the county SGI map does. In the tract map, most rural tracts are a shade of green while gray tracts tend to be suburban. Within a city itself, especially in Winston-Salem and Greensboro, wealthier parts of the city appear a shade of green while formerly redlined districts light up bright orange. This clearly shows that majority minority neighborhoods are severely underfunded relative to their more fortunate neighbors – a pattern that persists throughout nearly every developed part of the Triad.

Figure 6*North Carolina Triad Census Tracts Spending Gap Index (SGI) Map*

Note: This figure shows the distribution of the Spending Gap Index (SGI) throughout the 469 Triad US Census Tracts. A value of Good or Very Good means higher spending than need, a value of On Track means adequate spending for need, and a value of Poor or Very Poor means lower spending than need.

Discussion

As presented in the results section of the analysis, there is a significant clustering of public transit need, spending per capita, and especially the SGI. Specifically, US Census Tracts in formerly redlined areas are severely underfunded relative to their needs. In Census Tracts located in historically wealthy areas, public transit spending greatly exceeds public transit need. As shown by the SGI, there is a public policy incongruency with how public transit spending is allocated.

As I mentioned in the introduction of this paper, investments in public transportation can grow the local economy. Similarly, public transit can also improve household income by providing greater access to more job opportunities through increasing the geographic area a worker can reach. In the United States especially, these programs benefit impoverished populations because they allow people to navigate through car centric infrastructure, something that is impossible to do with just a bike or through walking. Therefore, to adequately support the

needs of their constituents, the governments of the Triad (most notably Winston-Salem, Greensboro, and High Point) need to address these spending gaps.

There are two ways to best adjust the current paradigm to better suit the needs of residents. The preferred way is to simply increase the number of bus lines or on-demand vehicles that serve currently underfunded neighborhoods. While this does increase the cities' overall budget, the gains in local GDP should offset the increase in spending that the city would need to contribute upfront. To start, the local governments should target those tracts with a designation of "*Very Poor*" to get the most impact per dollar spent.

The other way that local governments can address this problem without increasing spending in the long run is to divert current services away from the wealthier tracts towards tracts with higher poverty rates and higher public transit need. While this will have a steep upfront cost to restructure the system, in a few years it will cost roughly the same amount while having the added benefit of being more efficient relative to public transit need. People from the overfunded census tracts in Winston-Salem and Greensboro rarely (if ever) use the bus system so shifting where the money is spent should be politically feasible. However, local governments should be careful not to divert too much, or they might cause the currently overfunded tracts to become underfunded.

Closing Comments

Limitations

This analysis relies exclusively on secondary data sources, which introduces inherent limitations. Firstly, the American Community Survey (ACS) and other similar demographic datasets are inherently subject to sampling error, nonresponse bias, and other uncontrollable aspects. As a result, the variables used to estimate transit need may not perfectly reflect current conditions. Similarly, the most recent Federal Transit Administration's expenditure data represents reported spending for 2024.

Secondly, while dasymetric areal interpolation improves the spatial accuracy of estimates compared to simpler volume preserving methods, it is still an estimate that relies on assumptions about how each variable is distributed. The weighting scheme assumes that higher-density, developed areas receive proportionally more transportation resources, which may not reflect real-world allocation practices.

Third, the z-scores for levels of spending in each geographic unit analysis (whether it be counties, state house districts, state senate districts, or congressional districts) are calculated based on a comparison to other geographic areas of the state, rather than an area outside of the state. In other words, if all funding across the entire state were raised or lowered by the same amount, the z-scores would not change. This analytical decision was made because comparing

funding levels to jurisdictions outside the state would involve potential bias in the selection of what constitutes a comparable jurisdiction. However, it is important to keep in mind that this approach to calculating z-scores constrains the interpretation of the results to an intra-state comparison.

Finally, the two composite indices created, PCI and SGI, depend on the specific selected variables and the PCA-derived weights. While these indices provide a standardized measure of transit need relative to spending, they may oversimplify complex social dynamics. Therefore, the results of these indices should be interpreted as an indicator rather than as deterministic. Future work could incorporate additional variables, higher resolution data, or different weighting schemes to further refine these measures.

Reproducibility

To improve another researcher's ability to reproduce my findings, I have uploaded all computer code that I used, along with all source data downloaded, to a GitHub repository (Lackey, 2026). It is my hope that this will be useful and improve the transparency of this analysis. Similarly, all intermediate data products can be downloaded off my ArcGIS Online page or through the online dashboard created for this paper. This analysis was conducted using two different GIS programs – ArcGIS Pro and R Studio – and all the data wrangling and processing was conducted in R.

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Appendix A

Mathematical Justification for Volume-Preserving Areal Interpolation

A volume-preserving allocation satisfies the conservation condition where V_t is the volume of the target features and V_s is the volume of the source features:

$$\sum_t V_t = \sum_s V_s$$

That is, the sum of values across all target units equals the original total across source units. Areal weighting is the simplest volume-preserving method (Lin, 2015). Let A_s denote the area of a source unit, A_{ts} the area of overlap between source s and target t , and V_s the value in the source. The value assigned to each target under areal weighting is (Hawley, 2005):

$$V_t = \sum_{s=1}^n \left(\frac{V_s A_{ts}}{A_s} \right)$$

Because the proportions $\frac{A_{ts}}{A_s}$ sum to 1 across all intersecting units, the original total is constant.

By contrast, non-volume preserving methods have fallen out of favor in the past few decades as they distort useful geographic information. An example of a type of non-volume preserving method is total assignment where the full value of the source feature is assigned to every single intersecting target feature:

$$V_t = V_s$$

If a source unit intersects k target units, then total assignment amounts to:

$$\sum_{t=1}^k V_t = kV_s$$

Therefore, if any source unit is divided among multiple targets, the aggregate value across targets must exceed the original total:

$$\sum_t V_t > \sum_s kV_s \text{ when } k > 1$$

The magnitude of distortion relative to areal weighting can be expressed as a multiplier where every target unit has their own unique multiplier M . To calculate the value of each multiplier, a system of equations can be used. Let p be equal to the weighed proportion used in areal weighting. The distortion equation for the multiplier is therefore:

$$p = \frac{A_{ts}}{A_s}$$

$$M = \frac{V_s}{V_s p} = \frac{1}{p}$$

As p approaches 0, M approaches infinity. The distortion caused by non-volume preserving methods increases nonlinearly as overlap decreases. Importantly, because p depends solely on boundary geometry, inflation under total assignment is determined by how units intersect rather than by the underlying magnitude of the data.

To further illustrate this point using round integers rather than abstract equations, take a sample country with a GDP of \$1,000,000 with 10 states each occupying 10% of the country's land where the country is the source unit and the states the target. If one were to use a non-volume preserving method like total assignment, then for each state the full value of the country would be allocated such that:

$$V_t = V_s$$

$$\$1,000,000 = \$1,000,000$$

Because there are 10 states each intersecting the country, then total assignment amounts to:

$$\sum_{t=1}^k V_t = kV_s$$

$$\$10,000,000 = 10 * \$1,000,000$$

Returning to areal weighting, this volume preserving method results in a meaningfully different calculation for both each individual state and the whole system. For each individual state, the value is estimated relative to the proportion of country's total area such that:

$$V_t = \sum_s \left(\frac{V_s A_{ts}}{A_s} \right)$$

$$\$100,000 = \frac{\$1,000,000 * 10\%}{100\%}$$

Despite there being 10 states that intersect the country, the total dollars across each state remain equal to the GDP of the country.

$$\sum_t V_t = \sum_s V_s$$

$$10 * \$100,000 = \$1,000,000$$

Therefore, relative to volume preserving methods (in this case areal weighting), the non-volume preserving methods like total assignment overestimate each individual state and inflate the whole system's GDP by 10 times such that:

$$M = \frac{1}{p}$$
$$10 = \frac{1}{0.1}$$

Because of this, the volume preserving method accuracy maintains the GDP of the country while its counterpart, the non-volume preserving method, produces estimates that no longer correspond to the known system total.

In practice, this bias is unevenly distributed. For example, if the source units are counties and target units are state house districts, small urban districts that intersect portions of one or two high-value counties will receive repeated whole allocations under total assignment. Larger rural districts that align more closely with county boundaries will experience far less distortion. Consequently, non-volume preserving methods introduce systematic spatial bias, undermining comparability across districts and preventing recovery of original totals. For analysis using fiscal budgets or other types of expenditures, such distortions materially alter the conclusions that can be drawn (Tobler, 1979).

Appendix B

Mathematical Underpinning of Dasymetric Areal Aggregation

As discussed in Appendix A, volume preserving methods tend to make a set of assumptions about how the data is distributed throughout the system. In the case of the example method, areal weighting, utilizing this process assumes that a variable is perfectly distributed throughout the system relative to geographic area. That is, larger geographic areas have more of a thing than smaller geographic areas.

Of course, when working with real world data volume is never perfectly distributed in the ways that areal weighting assumes. This is especially apparent in census tract level data where geographically larger units often have less stuff than geographically smaller units. To address this problem, geographers have developed a dasymetric method that incorporates remote sensing data as a key to estimate variable distribution (Fisher, 1996). A typical dasymetric method adapts the areal weighting formula so that:

$$V_t = \sum_{s=1}^n \left(\frac{V_S R_{ts}}{R_s} \right)$$

In the context of their work, Fisher and Langford define R as residential pixels because their study investigates population density and distribution. However, this method can be redefined to fit whatever definition the researcher desires.

To estimate the distribution of public transit spending, I adapted Fisher's formula to focus on occupied pixels instead of residential pixels. For the purposes of this research, occupied pixels are defined according to the National Land Cover Database's (NLCD) definitions. This results in a simplified dasymetric areal aggregation formula of:

$$V_t = \sum_{s=1}^n \left(\frac{V_S O_{ts}}{O_s} \right)$$

where O_{ts} is the count of occupied cells within each target and source intersection while O_s is the same measure but for each source feature. This provides a similar structure to areal interpolation while masking out all non-developed cells.

However, this analysis took the equation a step further than Fisher and Langford did. To account for the likely differences in spending between high development and an open parking lot, I inserted weights for each of the four classes of development into the dasymetric formula. The resulting equation is as follows:

$$V_t = \sum_{s=1}^n \left(\frac{V_S * (O_1 * 0.25 + O_2 * 0.5 + O_3 * 0.75 + O_4 * 1)_{ts}}{(O_1 * 0.25 + O_2 * 0.5 + O_3 * 0.75 + O_4 * 1)_s} \right)$$

In this equation, with respect to the NLCD classifications, O_1 represents the count of all open space cells, O_2 represents the sum of all low intensity cells, O_3 represents the cumulative number of medium intensity cells, and finally O_4 represents the total high intensity cells in present in each feature. By using this weighting scheme, I can place more emphasis on highly developed urban areas than I do on sparsely developed suburban areas and attribute more of the total public safety spending to these regions which are closer to the reality than any equal weighting scheme might be.

Appendix C**Principal Component Analysis Summary Table***PCA Summary Table*

<i>Component</i>	Eigenvalue	Percent Variance Explained	Cumulative Percent Explained
<i>PC1</i>	2.898	32.2	32.2
<i>PC2</i>	1.573	17.48	49.67
<i>PC3</i>	1.434	15.93	65.61
<i>PC4</i>	0.899	9.99	75.59
<i>PC5</i>	0.81	9.0	84.6
<i>PC6</i>	0.469	5.21	89.81
<i>PC7</i>	0.419	4.66	94.46
<i>PC8</i>	0.385	4.27	98.74
<i>PC9</i>	0.114	1.27	100